

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILL OF STUDENTS OF HIGH EDUCATION THROUGH INTERNET TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: Listening is claimed to be the most difficult skill for foreign language learners. Thus, it needs an effective model of teaching to improve students' listening skill. The present study investigates the use of internet technology in improving listening skill of university students and examines the effectiveness of the use of internet technology in the teaching of listening by observing students' listening in the classroom.

Keyword: listening skill, internet technology, students of higher educational institutions.

Резюме. Аудирование считается самым сложным навыком для изучающих иностранный язык. Таким образом, необходима эффективная модель обучения для улучшения навыков слушания учащихся. В настоящем исследовании исследуется использование интернет-технологий для улучшения навыков аудирования у студентов университетов и изучается эффективность использования интернет-технологий в обучении аудированию путем наблюдения за слушанием студентов в классе.

Ключевые слова: навык аудирования, интернет-технологии, студенты высших учебных заведений.

Rezyume. Tinglab tushunish chet tilini o'rganuvchilar uchun eng qiyin mahoratdir. Shunday qilib, talabalarining tinglash qobiliyatini yaxshilash uchun samarali o'qitish modeli kerak. Ushbu tadqiqot universitet talabalarining tinglash qobiliyatini oshirishda internet texnologiyasidan foydalanishni o'rganadi va sinfda talabalarining tinglashini kuzatish orqali tinglashni o'rgatishda internet texnologiyasidan foydalanish samaradorligini o'rganadi.

Kalit so'z: tinglab tushunish qobiliyati, internet texnologiyasi, oliy ta'lim o'quv muassasasi talabalari.

Introduction. Listening is defined as the process of paying attention to what is heard and also trying to understand this speech or catch the meaning conveyed by the speaker. People use this skill almost every day to make a communication, to respond, answering the phone and watching TV, videos or listening radios, songs, and sending and accepting voice messages in social media. These examples are as proves that listening is an important skill to enable people to communicate with each other. From

this perspective, technology can give chances learners to access to listen to authentic materials in audio and video formats, real conversations, podcast and Ted talk applications, songs, interactive listening exercises. In fact, research shows that technology-supported listening not only enables skills but also teaches them at the same time, so that EFL students can grow their understanding of different speeches, accents, intonation, stress and so on when they listen to native speakers' speech by connecting the internet, they can also improve their pronunciation and understanding speed of speech.

Thus, this study was conducted to investigate the use of internet technology for students of high education in the teaching of listening. Particularly, the study examines listening practices commonly utilized by EFL teachers to teach listening skills for university students in EFL classrooms. Developments in technology in education are inevitable as technology has become an integral part of our everyday life. The new generations of students have a high level of technology literacy. Hence, it is important to investigate the teachers' perception on the use of internet technology in the teaching of listening classrooms as information regarding the benefits, implementation, and attitudes of teachers will be a further probe.

Literature review. It is important for teachers to define different ways to make learning processes significant and successful. Learning listening should be meaningful, as fostering the use of internet technology in EFL classrooms, should support the development of listening skill especially with students of high education. Having said this, the principal objective of this review is to define the main concepts in this research. It is important to clarify that these constructs are listening skill, and internet technology as the most effective tool. In addition, this review not only shows the definition of the concepts, but it also presents the principles of scholars in terms of listening as well as using internet technology in the classroom.

From the point of Brown (2006) listening comprehension is an interactive process in which through the development of strategies the listener can achieve goals. Moreover, to develop this skill students not only learn during the lessons, but also they must learn the other authentic materials in audio or video formats, to achieve this goal the role of teachers is different as they guide them learn new content.

According to Richards (2008), an approach to the teaching of listening that is predicted upon the following assumptions:

- Listening serves the goal of extracting meaning from messages
- In order to do this learners have to be taught how to use both bottom up and top down processes in arriving at an understanding of messages
- The language of utterances, i.e. the precise words, syntax, expressions, used by speakers are temporary carriers of meaning. Once meaning has been identified there is no further to attend to the form of messages. Learning to listening seems as a developmental process that helps students to listen and choose necessary statements.

Most of students of high education may find some difficulties in accomplishing their listening test. It is the most difficult skill for students to master. [Richards: 2008, p 2]

Furthermore, John Flowerdew states that technology is useful to teach listening because each type of technology provides opportunities for students to explore their ranges of listening strategies. And it allows for more emphasis on certain aspects, such as cross-cultural, interactional, critical, and contextual dimensions of listening, to be developed. Technology also makes learning process of listening more entertaining. He states that using new technologies can help us to teaching listening in foreign language.[John Flowerdew: 2005, p 182]

In addition, Peterson also highlights that the use of technology outside the language classroom or in the self-access centre can make learners more autonomous. One key feature of using technology in learning is that it allows language practice and study away from the confines of the classroom at your own pace anywhere: a hotel room, the office, an Internet café, at home or, of course, in the self-access language centre. New ICT skills learnt in the classroom (e.g. Internet search skills) can be transferred to real life. Using a range of ICT tools and a web-based environment can give learners exposure to practicing listening regularly, and consequently, become a more effective listener. The use of technology via web-based environment can be current, e.g. using a listening activity with today's news from news websites can add a dimension of immediacy to listening practice. While listening to digital audio or watching a video clip, learners have the opportunity to pause at will, and listen and read a transcript. Moreover, learners can get instant feedback on what they have done (e.g. you watch a video clip/listen to audio and check answers immediately after watching/listening). Learners can access authentic websites, as well as websites for EFL/ESL learners. As learners become used to selecting and evaluating listening materials, they are able to plan out their own use of web-based materials in their own time. By practicing this tools, learners can be good listener and independent learner. [Peterson: 2010, p. 139,154]

Taking into account the principles of writing, Nicolini developed main principles to structure how technology can support learning in the classroom environment. These principles provided a lens to view technology in listening classroom. They are as follows:

- ❑ Classroom instruction and information management can be strengthened through the efficient use of technology
- ❑ Technology can support student learning
- ❑ Students need to know how to access and select from the avalanche of information to help them solve problems
- ❑ Technology can and should facilitate the rethinking and the restructuring of what takes place in the classroom . [Nicolini: 2006, p. 67]

Based on these ideas, technology was viewed as effective tool in teaching listening as it gives students multiple uses of technology-mediated listening

opportunities that offer a variety of experiences and choices for high education students. Technology mediated listening in a socially constructed space allows students to listen a wide range of different speeches in a specific theme and communicating with peers by audio chats, teachers, and environments in addition to the technology itself.

Research methods. This study employed a qualitative research design in the form of descriptive case study in regard to the consideration that the researcher focused on the observing, interpreting, and understanding what the teacher and students did in listening class that used the internet. This was done to gain an in-depth understanding of the situation and meaning for those involved. The subjects of the study were students of high educational settlements that the English ability of the students is upper-intermediate.

The data was collected through non-participant observation. It was an observation in which the researcher only observed the process of teaching and learning. To obtain the data related to the use of internet technology in teaching listening, students' listening was taken to investigate their listening ability since the use of internet technology was expected to help students to understand real listening materials based on structure and language feature.

Analysis and result. This study sought to investigate the use of the internet technology in teaching listening to students of high education. It also investigated the development of students' listening abilities. From the result of the findings and discussion, it can be stated as follows.

The major conclusion of the study is that the use of the internet technologies as an aid in listening lessons is successfully applied in some ways. With respect to the internet use in teaching listening, it indeed gave benefits to the students as well the teacher. With the help of internet technologies, students can easily access to the internet during the lesson and can practice, do assignments sent by the teacher and also they can improve their listening skills self-study at home because there are a lot of internet resources which include podcast with transcriptions, interactive online exercises, even movies with subtitles.

Conclusion. It can be concluded that using internet technology for teaching listening affect a better result of listening performance for students of high education. To reach optimum listening achievement, not only the classroom environment should be provided by the internet access, but also teacher should provide specific sites for listening and determining the most current and hottest issues to teach listening. This can make each student be motivated and interested to master this skill. Thus, it is recommended that it is useful to use internet technology for classroom activities in teaching listening and it can improve the students' listening achievement.

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